

Product Knowledge and Product Compliance to Safety Standards as Determinants of Consumer Purchase of Organic Food Products in Anambra State, Nigeria

Amarachukwu Judith Ezeobi, Ph.D

Department of Marketing, Federal Polytechnic Oko, Anambra State, Nigeria

Okwuchukwu Marcus Anyasor, Ph.D

*Department of Marketing, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University,
Anambra State, Nigeria*

Peace Azuka Ezeh, Ph.D

*Department of Marketing, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University,
Anambra State, Nigeria*

Nkoli Augustina Chendo, Ph.D

*Department of Marketing, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University,
Anambra State, Nigeria*

Abstract

There has been a significant increase in consciousness, demand and consumption of organic food products in recent times particularly in Anambra State of Nigeria, which stem from the touted health benefits that it offers. Food grown organically are rich in nutrients. As convincing as this view may appear, one still wonders what actually motivates the consumers to purchase these products. Hence, the study investigated the determinants of consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State. The specific objectives of the study were to: ascertain the effects of product knowledge and product compliance to safety standards, use of organic food products in Anambra State. In line with the objectives of this study, two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study was anchored on the consumer behaviour theory propounded by Engel-Kollat-Blackwell (EKB). The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The study population comprised of the consumers of organic food products in Anambra State. The sample size of 384 was drawn using Cochran formula. The convenience sampling method was employed to select the respondents for the study. Structured questionnaire was used as the instrument of data collection. Instruments were designed by the researcher and scored on a four-point Likert Scale. The reliability of instrument used was test-retest and Cronbach Alpha Analysis. Descriptive statistics (frequency tables and percentages) were employed in analyzing the research questions, while multiple regression analysis was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used to process the data. The results of the study showed that product knowledge ($\beta=0.452$; $p<0.000$) had significant positive effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State. Product compliance to safety standards ($\beta =0.029$; $p>0.560$) was found to have no significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State. On the bases of the above findings, the study concluded that product knowledge is the more significant predictor while product compliance to safety standards is not a significant factor that affects consumer purchase of organic food products. The

study therefore recommended among others that stakeholders in the organic food production value chain should invest more to make organic food products available and also create awareness programmes to deepen consumer's knowledge about the benefits of consuming organic food while at the same time reappraise their safety standards.

Keywords: *Organic food products, Product knowledge, product compliance to safety standards, consumer purchase.*

JEL Classification codes: *L66, P36*

Suggested citation: Ezeobi, A.J., Anyasor, O.M., Ezech, P.A., & Chendo, N.A. (2025). Product Knowledge and Product Compliance to Safety Standards as Determinants of Consumer Purchase of Organic Food Products in Anambra State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(1), 68-82. DOI: 10.59324/ejmecb.2025.2(1).05

Introduction

Apparently, there has been a remarkable increase in the demand and consumption of organic food in recent times. Yesufu, Aremu and Adebayo (2018) reported that with increased health awareness and sensitization of consumers, there followed a corresponding increase in the demand for these products, especially among the comparatively educated and affluent segments of the society. Mohamad *et al.* (2014) and Gracia and De Magistris (2007) observed that significant majority of the consumers of organic products are found among urban settlers. Further, Acee-Eke and Ikegwuru (2020) and Mottaleb, Rahut, Kruseman and Erenstein (2018) attributed the surge in the demand and consumption of organic food products to population and income level expansion, as well as the clamour for environmental conservation. This is because as more people move into a geographical location, there is a tendency for demand for products to increase, correspondingly. Though there's a reported rise in the demand for organic food products notwithstanding, consumer quest for these products in this part of the world is still not clearly defined.

A look at the global market of organic food production and consumption reveals a fundamental gap between developed nations and the developing nations. As revealed in a comprehensive and extensive report by Exchange (2022), the global organic food and beverage market was valued at 188.35 billion dollars in 2021, with an expected increase of 13.0 % between 2022 and 2030. Data sourced from FiBL survey (2022) further revealed that the market is currently dominated by European, North American and Asian nations. Africa, on the other hand, had a relatively low stake in both the production and consumption of these food products (The Exchange, 2022).

Extant literature has provided some of the predictive variables that explain the rate of demand and consumption of organic food products: income level (Hansmann, Baur, & Binder, 2020; Di Vita, Pappalardo, Chinnici, La Via, & Damico, 2019), higher educational attainment (Shashi, Kottala, & Singh, 2015), as well as geographical considerations (Mohamad *et al.*, 2014) have been shown to be dominant. Consumer personal factors - self-concept, age and life cycle (Nouraie, Moorimeh, & Kordi, 2017); knowledge of product (Elsya & Indriyani, 2020; Ateke & Dibia, 2018; and product compliance to safety standards (Aslam & Hong, 2018). The consumer's knowledge of the product boosts confidence in the potency or efficiency of the product among others. Shayaa, Sulaiman, Ashraf, Jaafar, Zakaria, Wai and Chung (2018) found that when consumers are confident of a product, it stimulates behavioural intention to purchase. For organic food product to engender this behavioural intention to purchase there is need to examine whether the consumer's knowledge of the product is deep enough to trigger confidence and consequently demand and consumption of the said product.

Demand for goods and services are also influenced by the consumer's belief that the product meets set down safety standards (Aslam & Hong, 2018). Consumers naturally are concerned about their safety and general well-being thus, self-preservation and utility maximization considerations come uppermost when making purchase decisions (Hague & Hague, 2016). With the increased level of awareness and sensitization programmes financed by eco-friendly agencies and conservationist organizations, more emphasis has been placed on environmental considerations that possibly shape demand and consumption of goods and services. Consumers now seek sustainable satisfaction beyond immediate gratification as a result of considerations of human meddlesome activities with the ecosystem (Dimitrova, Ilieva & Angelova, 2022). Conservation and preservation of trees and several species of wildlife labeled as endangered are some of the themes employed by environmental rights groups as well as various activists in their recurrent crusades against consumption of various goods and services (Dimitrova *et al.*, 2022; Dangi, Gupta, & Narula, 2020).

Interestingly, there is a paucity of research on both the nature, direction and density of demand and consumption of organic products in Anambra State as focus has been on the actual production and techniques involved in the production of organic food (Obiesie, Komore & Moludu, 2022; Nenna & Ugwumba, 2014). This study therefore, becomes expedient to ascertain the consumer-oriented determinants of consumer purchase of organic food products.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the Model of Consumer Behaviour, referred to as EKB theory, developed by Engel James, Kollat David, and Blackwell Roger in 1968. Engel Kollat Blackwell consumer behaviour model assumed that the consumer is rational and seeks to maximise satisfaction from the goods and services consumed. The buyer, according to Engel *et al.* (1968) has a set of needs that are shaped by their personality, culture and social environment. Also, exposure to a range of stimuli, including marketing messages, product characteristics and environmental cues helps the consumer evaluate the options and selects the one that is most likely to satisfy their needs and desires, bearing in mind the social and environmental costs of such a decision. Thus, the EKB theory recognizes that both information and external factors such as social and environmental influences play a vital role in shaping purchase decisions.

Literature Review

Darsono *et al.* (2018) found that some of the consumer-oriented variables identified in this study; i.e., health concern product knowledge and quality, had significant effects on consumers purchase intentions for organic food products. However, emphasis was placed on consumer's attitude towards these products as a predictor of actual purchase. Also, Singh and Verma (2017) confirmed that four factors (health consciousness, knowledge, subjective norms, and price) influence the consumer attitude towards organic food products. However, purchase intention towards organic foods is affected by these four factors along with one additional factor (i.e., availability). The results showed that these five factors also influence the actual buying behaviour but attitude and purchase intention mediate the relationship. The findings of Imiru (2021) also identified knowledge about the product, safety and environmental friendliness as having significant effect on buying behaviour of organic food consumers. Elsy and Indriyani (2020) carried out research using quantitative method to examine the causal relationships between product knowledge, product information and repurchase intention of Tupperware products among housewives in Indonesia. The findings revealed that product knowledge affects repurchase intention in Tupperware products.

Studies on the association between product compliance to safety standards are available in extant studies. Ding, Li and Liu (2021) carried out an exploratory study to ascertain the influential factors on consumer purchase intention for organic foods. They found that the food value, safety and

positive emotions had different degrees of influence on consumers purchase intention. Furthermore, Yazar and Burucuoğlu, (2019) carried out a survey study on consumer attitude towards organic foods across genders in Turkey. Findings revealed that attitude toward organic food is a powerful indicator of the consumers' intention to purchase organic food. Health consciousness, food safety concerns, attitudes, and intentions have a significant relationship with each other. As a result of the gender based binary model comparison, the attitudes and intentions of male and female consumers towards organic food are different. Acee-Eke and Ikegwuru (2020) examined consumers' demand for organic food products and purchase intentions. Findings revealed that food safety concern was the strongest predictor of purchase intentions, followed by environmental concern, and the last emerged as health consciousness. Also, consumers demand for organic food products had positive and significant influence on purchase intentions through food safety concern, environmental concern, and health consciousness. Furthermore, Khanal (2020) examined consumers' willingness, behaviours and attitudes to pay a price premium for local organic foods in Nepal. Findings revealed that .91% .45% of the respondents were willing to pay more for organic food products because of several factors including food safety concerns, health consciousness and environmental concerns.

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the extent of effect of product knowledge on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.
2. Ascertain the level of effect of product compliance to safety standards on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State;

Research Questions

1. To what extent does product knowledge influence consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State?
2. What level of effect has product compliance to safety standards on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State?

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Product knowledge has no significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

Ha₁: Product knowledge has a significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Product compliance to safety standards has no significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

Ha₂: Product compliance to safety standards has a significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

Methods

Design

This study adopted a descriptive research design using survey method. The survey involved interviewing a sample of the population of the study area using the questionnaire.

Population

The population of the study comprises of all consumers of organic food products (farm produce-natural: yam, fruits, vegetables; processed: garri, rice, palm oil) in the twelve major markets (four (4) drawn from each of the three senatorial zones) of Anambra State namely; Ochanja Market, Onitsha; Relief Market, Okpoko; Nkwo, Ose-Okwodu, Onitsha; Ekeigwe Market, Nteje; Eke Ekwulobia; Nkwo Nnewi; Nkwo-Ogbe, Ihiala; Nkwo Umunze; Eke Awka; Afor Nkpor; Afor Agulu and; Oyeagu Abagana.

Participants

A sample size of 384 was obtained using Cochran (1963) technique for unknown populations. Allocation was done on the basis of researcher's estimated size of the market in judgmental consideration of the city/town of location. Thus, markets located in bigger cities got higher quota, and downwards. In the light of the above, markets located in Anambra North and Anambra Central were allocated higher sample size because of their unique position as the economic hub of the State, and State Capital territory respectively. The Convenience Sampling Technique was employed in selecting the 384 respondents for the study.

Measures

The research instrument for this study was a structured questionnaire. This instrument was divided into sections A and B. Section A sought for the respondent's demographic information, while section B solicited for responses/opinions on the specified objectives of the study. The section B consists of thirty (30) question items with responses scored on a 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD), weighted at 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Reliability

To ascertain the internal consistency of the research instrument, the researcher in a test-retest mode, administered copies of the questionnaire to 30 pilot respondents drawn from three markets in Anambra State namely Main Market Onitsha, Orié Uga, and Nkwo Adazi, with a repeat after two weeks. These respondents share similar characteristics with the study population. The scores obtained from 1st and 2nd tests were subjected to Cronbach Alpha Analysis. The reliability result showed average coefficient value of 0.8733 which indicated acceptable reliability based on the assumption that any reliability coefficient above 0.75 is adequate, Nworgu (2015).

Method of Data Analysis

The data was presented in frequency tables and analysed using descriptive statistics (percentages and mean). Multiple regression was used to test the hypotheses at 5% level of significance to determine the nature of significance of the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The analyses was processed with the help of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26.

Results

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents by Characteristics (Demographics)

Demographics	Range/option	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-30years	34	10.2
	31-40years	88	26.5
	41-50years	124	37.3

	Above 50years Total	86 332	25.9 100
Gender	Male	98	29.5
	Female	234	70.5
	Total	332	100
Education Qualification	FSLC	100	30.1
	WASC/NECO/NABTEB	74	22.3
	Degree/HND/OND/NCE	82	24.7
	Post Degree	76	22.9
	Total	332	100
Marital Status	Single	74	22.3
	Married	248	74.7
	Divorced/Separated	6	1.8
	Widowed	4	1.2
	Total	332	100
Occupation	Farming	50	15.1
	Business	228	68.7
	Employed in private sector	26	7.8
	Civil/Public Servant	10	3.0
	Others	18	5.4
	Total	332	100
Average monthly income level	Below ₦30,999	52	15.7
	₦31,000-₦70,999	120	36.1
	₦71,000-₦99,999	110	33.1
	₦100,000-₦200,000	30	9.0
	Above ₦200,000	20	6.0
	Total	332	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 1 indicates that out of the 332 respondents whose questionnaire copies and data are being used in this analysis 34(10.2%) are within the age range of 18-30years; 88(26.5%) of the respondents are within the age bracket of 31-40 years; 124(37.3%) of the respondents are within the age bracket of 41-50years while 86(25.9%) of the respondents are above 50years. Table 4.1.1 result portrays that majority of the respondents fall within the age bracket of 31- 50 years. This implies that youth, strong and healthy adults purchase organic food products more when compared with underage and elderly people.

Table 1 also indicates that 98 representing (29.5%) of the respondents are males while 234 representing (70.4%) of the respondents are females. This shows that both sex were represented and also participated in the survey, although greater number of the respondents are females. This signals that females are more likely to purchase organic food products from the markets than their male counterparts.

A careful look at Table 1 demonstrates that 100 representing (30.1%) of the respondents had FSLC; 74 representing (22.3%) of the respondents had either WASC/NECO/NABTEB. 82 representing (24.7%) of the respondents had Degree or HND or OND or NCE as the highest education qualification obtained. 76 representing (22.9%) of the respondents had a Post Degree as the highest education qualification obtained. The implication of this is that majority of the respondents had formal education and that they are knowledgeable enough to ascertain how the study variables affect their purchase of organic food products.

On the respondents' profile on marital status; Table 1 revealed that 248 representing (74.7%) of the respondents are married; 74 representing (22.3%) of the respondents are single; 6 representing (1.8%) of the respondents are either divorced or separated; 4 representing (1.2%) of the respondents are widowed. This implies that both single and married people were represented and

also participated in the survey as well as divorced and widowed people. Based on table 4.1.1, greater number of the respondents surveyed is married.

Table 1 further indicates that out of 332 respondents validly surveyed and returned for analysis, 50 representing (15.1%) of the respondents are farmers; 228(68.7%) of the respondents are engaged in business; 26 representing (7.8%) of the respondents are employed in the private sector. 10 representing (3.0%) of the respondents are civil/public servants while 18 representing (5.4%) of the respondents engaged in other occupation. Based on result as depicted on table 4.1.1, majority of the respondents are business people. This implies sizeable number of the populace have something doing which entails that they can afford to purchase organic food products.

Regarding the average monthly income range, Table 1 also depicts that 52 representing (15.7%) of the respondents earn average monthly income below ₦30,999; 120 representing (36.1%) of the respondents get an average monthly income range of ₦31,000 – ₦70,999; 110 representing (33.1%) of the respondents get average monthly income range of ₦71,000 – ₦99,999; 30 representing (9.0%) of the respondents get average monthly income range of ₦100,000- ₦200,000 while 20 representing (6.0%) of the respondents get average monthly income range of above ₦200,000. This implies that consumers can afford to purchase organic food products comfortably in Anambra State.

Table 2. Responses on Product Knowledge (PKN)

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Mean
I am aware of quality of organic food products I purchase in the market.	252 (75.9%)	78 (23.5%)	2 (0.6%)	-	332	3.75
Price knowledge influences my purchase of organic food.	216 (65.1%)	114 (34.3%)	2 (0.6%)	-	332	3.64
I know that organic food products are fresh.	222 (66.9%)	108 (32.5%)	-	2 (0.6%)	332	3.66
I know that the taste of organic food product is good.	194 (58.4%)	132 (39.8%)	2 (0.6%)	4 (1.2%)	332	3.55
I know that organic food products are nutritious.	230 (69.3%)	98 (29.5%)	-	4 (1.2%)	332	3.67
Overall Mean						3.654

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2 shows that out of 332 respondents validly used in this analysis, 252 representing (75.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they are aware of the quality of organic food products they purchase in the market. 78 representing (23.5%) agreed that they are aware of the quality of organic food products they purchase in the market while 2 representing (0.6%) disagreed that they are aware of the quality of organic food products they purchase in the market. This implies that majority of the respondents strongly concurred that they know the value they get in purchasing organic food products in Anambra State.

A cursory look at Table 2 portrays that 216 representing (65.1%) of the respondents strongly agreed that knowledge about the price of organic food products influence their purchase actions. 114 representing (34.3%) of the respondents agreed that knowledge about the price of organic food products influence their purchase actions. 2 representing (0.6%) of the respondents disagreed that knowledge about the price of organic food products influence their purchase behaviour. This implies that majority of the respondents strongly believed that price knowledge is a significant factor that influence them to purchase organic food products in Anambra State.

An examination of field survey data presented on Table 2 indicates that 222 representing (66.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed that organic food products are fresh. 108 representing (32.5%) of the respondents agreed that that organic food products are fresh while 2 representing (0.6%) of the respondents strongly disagreed that that organic food products are fresh This implies that majority of the respondents strongly held that organic food products are fresh.

Table 2 also shows that 194 representing (58.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the taste of organic food product is good; 132 representing (39.8%) of the respondents agreed that the taste of organic food product is good; 2 representing (0.6%) of the respondents disagreed that the taste of organic food product is good while 4 representing (1.2%) of the respondents strongly disagreed that the taste of organic food product is good. The implication of the field survey finding on this parameter is that majority of the respondents strongly confirmed that the taste of organic food product is nice.

Furthermore, Table 2 demonstrates that 230 representing (69.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed that organic food products are nutritious; 98 representing (29.5%) of the respondents agreed that organic food products are nutritious while 4 representing (1.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed that organic food products are nutritious. This implies that majority of the respondents strongly agreed that organic food products are nutritious. In addition, the grand mean for product knowledge indicators is 3.654. This implies that on the average, respondents strongly agreed that they are knowledgeable about organic food products in Anambra State.

Table 3. Responses on Product Compliance to Safety Standards (PCSS)

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Mean
I believe that organic products are tested by the regulatory authority.	214 (64.5%)	68 (20.5%)	44 (13.3%)	6 (1.8%)	332	3.48
I know that organic food products are approved by standard organization of Nigeria.	138 (41.6%)	40 (12.0%)	78 (23.5%)	76 (22.9%)	332	2.72
I am aware that NAFDAC gives seal of approval for the consumption of organic products.	134 (40.4%)	66 (19.9%)	72 (21.7%)	60 (18.1%)	332	2.83
Organic food products are verified by the Ministry of Agriculture.	164 (49.4%)	80 (24.1%)	50 (15.1%)	38 (11.4%)	332	3.11
I know that organic food products have regulatory guidelines.	158 (47.6%)	96 (28.9%)	60 (18.1%)	18 (5.4%)	332	3.19
Overall Mean						3.066

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Data in Table 3 revealed that out of the 332 respondents involved in this study, 214 (64%) strongly agreed that organic food products are tested by regulatory authorities, 68 (20.5%) agreed that they believed regulatory authorities test organic food products, 44 (13.3%) disagreed, while 6 respondents representing 1.8% of the entire sample strongly disagreed that organic products are tested by regulatory agencies. This indicated that a majority of the respondents are in agreement that organic food products are tested by regulatory authorities.

Furthermore, Table 3, on approval of organic food products by the Standard Organization of Nigeria, 138 respondents representing 41.6% of the 332 respondents strongly agreed, 40 (12%) agreed; 78(23.5.5%) disagreed while 76 (22.9%) strongly disagreed. A breakdown of the responses revealed that majority of the respondents, strongly agreed that organic food products are approved by the Standard Organization of Nigeria.

A further look at Table 3 revealed the level of awareness that NAFDAC issues seal of approval for the consumption of organic food products. 134 (40.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed, 66 (19.9%) of the respondents agreed, 72 (21.7%) disagreed, while 60 (18.1%) of 332 respondents strongly disagreed. This implied that the majority of the respondents strongly concurred that NAFDAC issues seal of approval for the consumption of organic food products in Anambra State.

A further examination of Table 3 showed 164 (49.4%) of the entire 332 respondents strongly agreed that organic food product are verified by the Ministry of Agriculture, 80 (24.1%) agreed, 50 respondents representing (15.1%) disagreed while 38 (11.4%) strongly disagreed that organic food product are verified by the Ministry of Agriculture. The results implies that a majority of the respondents strongly agreed that organic food products are verified by the Ministry of Agriculture.

Table 3 also revealed that 158 (47.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they know that organic food products have regulatory guidelines, 96 (28.9%) agreed, 60 (18.1%) disagreed, while 18(5.4%) of the 332 respondents strongly disagreed that they know that organic food products have regulatory guidelines. Therefore, it could be surmised that a majority of the respondents strongly agreed that they know that organic food products have regulatory agencies in Anambra State. In addition, the grand mean for product compliance to safety standards is 3.066. This implies that on the average, respondents strongly agree that they are aware of compliance of Organic food products to safety standards.

Table 4. Responses on Consumer Purchase of Organic Food Products (CP)

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Mean
I purchase organic products because of the knowledge I have about them.	216 (65.1%)	110 (33.1%)	6 (1.8%)	-	332	3.63
I purchase organic food because of their compliance to safety standards.	182 (54.8%)	142 (42.8%)	8 (2.4%)	-	332	3.52
I purchase organic products because I trust the viability of the products.	208 (62.7%)	114 (34.3%)	6 (1.8%)	4 (1.2%)	332	3.58
I purchase organic products because they are ideal for consumption.	184 (55.4%)	102 (30.7%)	24 (7.2%)	22 (6.6%)	332	3.35
I purchase organic products because of the awareness programmes done by sellers.	160 (48.2%)	78 (23.5%)	62 (18.7%)	32 (9.6%)	332	3.10
Overall Mean						3.436

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 4 reveals that out of the 332 respondents used for this study, 216 representing 65.1% strongly agreed that they purchase organic food products because of the knowledge they have about them, 110 (33.1%) agreed, while 6 (1.8%) disagreed. Therefore, it could be seen that a majority of the subjects agreed that they buy organic food products because of the knowledge they have about the products.

In addition, Table 4 also showed that 182 (54.8%) respondents strongly agreed that they purchased organic food products because of product compliance to safety standards, 142 (42.8%) agreed, while 8 (2.4%) disagreed. This revealed that a majority of the respondents bought organic food products because of the product compliance to safety standards.

Table 4 also revealed that 208 (62.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they purchase organic food products because of the viability of the products, 114 (34.3%) agreed, 6(1.8%) disagreed, while 4 (1.2%) strongly disagreed. From this result, it is clear that a majority of the respondents strongly agreed that they purchased organic food products because of their viability of the products.

Table 4 revealed that 184 respondents which represents 55.4% of the study sample strongly agreed that they purchased organic food products because they are ideal for consumption, 102 (30.7%) agreed; 24(7.2%) disagreed, while 22 (6.6%) strongly disagreed. A majority of the respondents strongly agreed that they purchased organic food products because they are ideal for consumption.

Finally, Table 4 also revealed that 160 (48.2% respondents strongly agreed that they purchased organic food products because of the awareness programmes on the benefits of consumption, 78 (23.5%) agreed, 62 (18.7%) disagreed while 32 (9.6%) strongly disagreed. This implies that a majority of the respondents strongly agreed that their purchase of organic food product is as a result of awareness programmes. Furthermore, with a grand mean of 3.436, it could be inferred that the respondent's purchase of organic food is determined by product knowledge, product compliance to safety standard, product viability, ideality for consumption and awareness programmes.

Correlation Analysis of the Study Variables

Table 5. Correlations Matrix

		CP	PKN	PCSS
CP	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	332		
PKN	Pearson Correlation	.747	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	332	332	
PCSS	Pearson Correlation	.201	.215	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.050	.102	
	N	332	332	332

Source: SPSS Computation Output, 2024.

Table 5 shows the relationships between the dependent variable and the independent variables used in the study. The relationship between the dependent variable and each of the exogenous variables are presented accordingly. The correlation analysis result indicates that product knowledge has an absolute value of 0.747 with a corresponding p-value of 0.000. This implies that PKN has a strong significant and positive relationship with consumer purchase of organic food products. The correlation result shows that product compliance to safety standards has an absolute value of 0.201 with a corresponding p-value of 0.050. This implies that PCSS has a low but positive relationship with consumer purchase of organic food products.

In addition, Pearson coefficient of correlation was also use to check whether the independent variables used in this study are perfectly correlated. Table 5 shows that all the independent variables used in this study exhibited no case of collinearity. The result as presented on table 5 showed that no independent variables perfectly correlate with one another. This portrays that the variables are not the same or similar but they are unique and differ which enable them to predict the dependent or endogenous construct independently and exclusively without relating to other explanatory variables accordingly. Therefore, there is no issue of multi-collinearity among the exogenous

variables since none of the independent variables was highly correlated with each other or measures the same thing.

Multiple Regression Analysis Result

Table 6. Regression Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.736 ^a	.687	.676	1.851	2.004
a. Predictors: (Constant), PKN, PCSS					
b. Dependent Variable: CP					

Table 7. Multiple Regression Coefficients Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Remark	Decision
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	.659	1.691		3.390	.002		
	PKN	.477	.084	.452	4.482	.000	Significant	Accept H _A
	PCSS	.016	.028	.029	.584	.560	Not significant	Accept H ₀
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Purchase of Organic Food Products (CP).								

Source: SPSS Computation Output, 2024.

Table 6 presents the regression model summary result. The overall regression correlation (R) value of 0.736 implies that a very strong relationship exists between the dependent and independent variables of this study. The R-Squared is the coefficient of determination or measure of goodness of fit of the regression model. The (R²) value is 0.687 which shows that the independent variables jointly were able to explain/effect or determine up to 68.7% of the variations/changes in the dependent variable leaving the remaining 31.3% variations to other factors or variables not captured by the model which will be taken care of by the stochastic error term. Furthermore, the adjusted R² value is 0.676 which means that even though an adjustment has been made in the explanatory variables, the independent variables were able to account for about 67.6% changes in the dependent variable. In addition, Durbin-Watson test measures the presence or absence of auto-correlation among the constructs. Based on the result on table 6, the Durbin-Watson statistics value is apparently 2.004. This implies that there is no auto-correlation among the explanatory parameters in the model. In other words, there is absence of auto correlation in the model. The implication is that each of the variables is distinct from each other as no two variables is measuring the same thing or perfectly related.

Furthermore, table 7 presents the regression coefficients results which shows the contribution, direction, strength, effect as well as the significance or otherwise of each of the independent variables on the dependent. The standardized coefficient (β) as shown on table 4.2.5 measures the individual coefficient, direction, magnitude or extent of effect as well as the percentage contribution of each of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The t-value and p-value measure the significance or otherwise of each of the independent variables on the dependent. Based on the results on table 4.2.5, all the independent variables have significant and positive effects on the dependent variable except product compliance to safety standards which has a positive but insignificant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Product knowledge has no significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

H_{a1}: Product knowledge has a significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

Based on result on Table 7, the absolute t-statistic value for product knowledge (PKN) is 4.482 with its corresponding p-value of 0.000. Since 0.000 is less than the stipulated level of significance of 0.05 used as the benchmark for this study; alternate hypothesis one (H_{a1}) is accepted while null hypothesis one (H₀₁) which states that product knowledge has no significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State is rejected. This implies that product knowledge has a significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Product compliance to safety standards has no significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

H_{a2}: Product compliance to safety standards has a significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

Based on result on Table 7, the absolute t-statistic value for product compliance to safety standards (PCSS) is 0.584 with its corresponding p-value of 0.560. Since 0.560 is greater than the stipulated level of significance of 0.05 used as the benchmark for this study; null hypothesis two (H₀₂) is accepted while alternative hypothesis two (H_{a2}) which states that product compliance to safety standards has a significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State is rejected. This implies that product compliance to safety standards has no significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State.

Discussion of Findings

Based on objective no. 1 and tested hypothesis no. 1, product knowledge has a significant and positive effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State. This implies that knowledge consumers have about an organic food product is a core determinant of the said consumers' organic food purchase. This finding supports the tenets of the EKB theory that hold that consumers internalize the knowledge they acquire about a product, build up knowledge based on the information and make rational purchase decisions thereof.

Several studies are in support of the finding in this present study. Darsono *et al.* (2018) found that consumer attitude and actual purchase behaviour were shaped by product knowledge, among others. Knowledge about a particular product engenders trust. Organic food products consumers are more likely to spend on products they have knowledge of and consequently trust. Wang *et al.* (2019) also concurred with the findings of the present study as they found that product knowledge positively moderates the relationship among social norms, personal attitude and organic food purchase intentions. Singh and Verma (2017) equally observed that product knowledge influences the actual buying behaviour of organic food product, this align with the findings of this study. This finding also reinforce the observation of Elsyia *et al.* (2020) that found product knowledge to affect repurchase intention in Tupperware products among housewives.

Furthermore, Imiru (2021) noted that knowledge about organic food products serve as a core determinant of consumer buying behaviour of organic food products, as information about organic food products helps consumers to make a better choice. Therefore, products knowledge, based on

the findings of this study have a strong and significant effect on consumers' purchase of organic food product because of its positive (+) contribution in the table, as suggested by extant studies.

Also, based on objective no. 2 and tested hypothesis no. 2, product compliance to safety standards has no significant but positive effect on consumer purchase of organic food product in Anambra State. This shows that product compliance to safety standards has no significant effect on their consumer purchase of organic food products. This finding is incongruent with the assumption of the EKB model of consumer behaviour that holds that consumers' perception and attitude is embodied in the cognitive schema they form as a result of the information they have about a product. Consumers' perception that an organic food product is safe for consumption is triggered by the confidence they have in the product compliance to safety standards. However, this study found that the product's compliance to safety standards has no significant effect on the actual purchase of organic food product. Nevertheless, the findings of the study are in agreement with Ding *et al.* (2021) that food value safety did not significantly impact purchase intentions of consumers. It is instructive to note that the gender composition of the present study could play a role in the current findings. Yazar and Burucoglu (2019) noted that there are gender differences in the consumers' attitude towards food safety and organic food products purchase intentions. With the gender disparity of 70.5% and 29.5% for female and male respondents, respectively, the incongruence between the expected findings and the actual findings of the study could be attributed to gender related factors. Pandurangarao *et al.* (2017) found that product safety influences customers to buy organic food, which is contrary to the findings of this study. Acee-Eke and Ikegwuru (2020) found that food safety concern was the strongest predictor of purchase intentions of organic food product. This is contrary to the findings of this present study where product compliance to safety standards has no significant (-) effect on consumer purchase of organic food product in Anambra State.

Khanal (2020) also found food safety to be a core determinant of purchase intentions. This may be as a result of the fact that the current study focuses on actual purchase of organic food product while, the reviewed study focused on consumers' willingness to pay above the regular price of conventional food.

Conclusion

This study have provided a considerably substantial knowledge and in-depth understanding that positive and significant effect exists between the dependent and independent variables used in this study. The study therefore concluded that product knowledge had a positive significant effect on consumer purchase of organic food products in Anambra State of Nigeria. Product compliance to safety standards had a positive but not significant effect on consumer purchase of organic products in Anambra State of Nigeria. The conclusion drawn from the findings of this study is that product knowledge is the more significant predictor while product compliance to safety standards is not a significant factor that affects consumer purchase of organic products.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The producers of organic food products, the dealers or sellers and other stakeholders should continue to enlighten the consumers so that they will be more knowledgeable about the quality, price and attributes of organic food products in Anambra State, Nigeria.

2. Government should take more disciplinary measures so as to make sure that producers of organic food products comply with safety standards.
3. The producers of organic food products, the sellers and other stakeholders should continue to make organic products available in the markets and more accessible strategic distribution outlets, for enhanced purchase actions.
4. The manufacturers and marketers of organic food products should continue to educate the masses more on the benefits of intake of organic food products that reduces chronic diseases in our bodies, chemical intake and protect our bodies from disease contamination.

References

- Acee-Eke, B. C., & Ikegwuru, M. C. (2020). Consumers demand for organic food products and purchase intentions: Empirical evidence from a consumer survey in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Marketing Systems*, 13(7), 1–18. Retrieved February 23, 2023, from <http://www.arcnjournals.org/images/ARCN-IJMMS-13-7-1.pdf>
- Ateke, B. W., & Dibia, J. U. D. (2018). Consumer knowledge and purchase intention of healthcare product consumers in River State. *International Journal of Business and Law Research*, 6(1), 1–7. Retrieved February 24, 2023, from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Consumer-Knowledge-and-Purchase-Intention-of-in/02e1557b3066478d89a8cf1af4aac0fe2008f54f>
- Aslam, W., & Hong, C. (2019). Study on consumer behaviour and food safety of organic products in Pakistan. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 78, 02021. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/20197802021>
- Dangi, N., Gupta, S. K., & Narula, S. A. (2020). Consumer buying behaviour and purchase intention of organic food: A conceptual framework. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 31(6), 1515–1530. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-01-2020-0014>
- Darsono, N., Yahya, A., Muzammil, A., Musnadi, S., Anwar, C., & Irawati, W. (2018). Consumer actual purchase behaviour for organic products in Aceh, Indonesia. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 292, 265–275. Retrieved February 23, 2023, from <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>
- Dimitrova, T., Ilieva, I., & Angelova, M. (2022). Exploring factors affecting sustainable consumption behaviour. *Administrative Sciences*, 12(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci12040155>
- Ding, H., Li, H., & Liu, X. (2021). The influential factors on consumer purchase intention for organic food in China: A case study on Bei Da Huang Organic Food Company. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 203, 2155–2161. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.211209.353>
- Di Vita, G., Pappalardo, G., Chinnici, G., La Via, G., & D’Amico, M. (2019). Not everything has still been explored: Further thoughts on additional price for the organic wine. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 231, 520–528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.05.268>
- Elsya, P., & Indriyani, R. (2020). The impact of product knowledge and product involvement to repurchase intention for Tupperware products among housewives in Surabaya, Indonesia. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 76, 01037. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20207601037>
- The Exchange. (2022). Africa in pale position to grow organic food market share. Retrieved February 20, 2023, from <https://theexchange.africa/industry-and-trade/africa-organic-food-market/>

- Gracia, A., & de Magistris, T. (2007). Organic food product purchase behaviour: A pilot study for urban consumers in the South of Italy. *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*, 5(4), 439–451. <https://doi.org/10.5424/sjar/2007054-5356>
- Hague, P., & Hague, N. (2016). *Customer satisfaction survey: The customer experiences through the customer's eyes*. London: Cogent Publication.
- Hansmann, R., Baur, I., & Binder, C. R. (2020). Increasing organic food consumption: An integrating model of drivers and barriers. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 275, 123058. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123058>
- Imiru, G. A. (2021). Determinants of consumer's buying behaviour of organic food products in relation to the mediating role of consumer buying intention in Ethiopia. *Journal of Business and Management*, 23(8), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.9790/487X-2308030117>
- Khanal, S. (2020). Consumers' willingness, behaviours and attitudes to pay a price premium for local organic foods in Nepal. *International Journal of Environment, Agriculture and Biotechnology*, 5(3), 594–609. Retrieved July 20, 2022, from <https://ijcab.com>
- Mohamad, S. S., Rusdi, S. D., & Hashim, N. H. (2014). Organic food consumption among urban consumers: Preliminary results. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 130, 509–514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.059>
- Mottaleb, K. A., Rahut, D. B., Kruseman, G., & Erenstein, O. (2018). Evolving food consumption patterns of rural and urban households in developing countries: A Bangladesh case. *British Food Journal*, 120(2), 392–408. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-12-2016-0620>
- Nenna, M. G., & Ugwumba, C. O. A. (2011). Utilisation of organic farming technologies among small-scale farmers in Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture Innovations and Research*, 3(1), 262–266. Retrieved February 20, 2023, from <https://ijair.org/index.php/component/jresearch/?view=publication&task=show&id=320&Itemid=166>.
- Nourai, M., Moorimeh, H. Y., & Kordi, J. (2017). Investigating the effects of personal factors on the customers' purchasing decision. *Kuwait Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 6(7), 8–16. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0018210>
- Nworgu, B. G. (2019). *Educational research: Basic issues and methodology*. Nsukka: University Trust Publishers.
- Obiesie, C. I., Komolafe, O. J., & Meludu, N. T. (2022). Profitability of organically produced fluted pumpkin among smallholder farmers in Anambra State. *IOSR Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science*, 15(2), 09–17. <https://doi.org/10.9790/2380-1502010917>
- Shashi, Kottala, S. V., & Singh, R. (2015). A review of sustainability, deterrents, personal values, attitudes and purchase intentions in the organic food supply chain. *Pacific Scientific Review*, 1(3), 114–123. Retrieved May 8, 2023, from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psrl.2016.09.003>
- Singh, A., & Verma, P. (2017). Factors influencing Indian consumers' actual buying behaviour towards organic food products. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 167, 473–483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.08.106>
- Yazar, E. E., & Burucuoğlu, M. (2019). Consumer attitude towards organic foods: A multigroup analysis across genders in Turkey. *Istanbul Business Research*, 48(2), 176–196. <https://doi.org/10.26650/ibr.2019.48.0001>

